

SNEHANA KARMA IN URDHWAJATRUGATA VIKARAS

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ABSTRACT

Shalakyta tantra is a specialised discipline of Ayurveda that focuses on the diagnosis, treatment and prevention of diseases related to the organs above the clavicle, focusing on the head, neck, eyes, ears, nose, and throat. It emphasises maintaining the integrity and optimal functioning of the sensory organs, which are vital for perception and communication. *Ayurveda* explains two types of treatment modalities i.e., *santarpana* & *apatarpana chikitsa*. *Snehana* is one among the *santarpana chikitsa* which is a fundamental procedure in *panchakarma*. It involves the application and ingestion of medicated oils and ghee to lubricate and soften the body's tissues, easing the removal of toxins. *Snehana* plays a crucial role in the management of *shalakyta rogas* chiefly *vata* predominant diseases. It can be practiced as both *bahya*(external) and *abhyantara*(internal) *chikitsa* in which *bahya snehana* is called as *Abhyanga* which is done along with *Svedana* after the completion of *Abyantara Snehana*. *Snehana* is also used as *Pradhana karma* which plays a pivotal role in preparing the body for effective detoxification and enhancing the success of later panchakrama therapies. It is also a major preparatory procedure to be performed before *shodhana*. The entire *shodhana* procedure depends upon the proper mobilization of *dosha* from the *sakha*, which is achieved with the help of *snehana* and *svedana*. Few of the external *snehana* procedures are also practiced as a part of *Dinacharya* and *Ritucharya* for the maintenance of health in a healthy person. Overall, the practice of *snehana* in *Shalakyta rogas* is an integral part of *Ayurvedic* treatment, contributing to the integrated approach of addressing both the symptoms and underlying causes of diseases.

KEYWORDS: *Snehana, Santarpana, Apatarpana, Shalakyta rogas, Bahya snehana, Abhyantara snehana, Shodhana, Samana.***INTRODUCTION**

Snehana Karma, one among the Purvakarmas of Panchakarma, plays a pivotal role in maintaining the health and function of the sensory organs. In Urdhwajatrugata Vikara, Snehana acts by pacifying Vata and Pitta doshas, promoting smooth functioning of the sensory pathways, and enhancing the clarity of perception. By improving tissue lubrication and promoting regeneration, it serves as both a preventive and curative measure for disorders such as Netra Roga, Karna Roga, Nasa Roga and Mukha Roga. Snehana Karma not only supports therapeutic interventions but also contributes to maintaining the vitality, stability and optimal performance of the Indriyas. *Snehana* is explained under one among the *shad upakramas* which

can be included under both *shodhana* and *samana chikitsa*.^[2]**AIMS AND OBJECTIVES**

- To elaborate and to understand the importance of *snehana karma* in *urdhwajatrugata vikaras*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

All the necessary information will be collected from different ayurvedic books, journals and from dissertations. The details of different *snehana karma* and its indications are discussed in detail.

SNEHANA IN URDHWAJATRUGATA VIKARAS ETYMOLOGY OF SNEHA AND SNEHANA

The word “*Sneha*” is derived from

स्निह् धातु + घञ् प्रत्यय (वाचस्पत्य)

Sneha: Oiliness, unctuousness, fattiness, greasiness, viscosity

Definition

Snehana is the procedure which imparts oiliness or unctuousness to the body.^[3]

Methods of introducing *sneha* into *shareera*

Sneha can be administered through *Sneha Pana*, *anuvāsana*, *mastishka*, *Shiro Basti*, *Uttara Basti*, *nasya*, *Karna purana*, *abhyanga* & *bhojana*.^[4]

Table 1: Classification of Snehana

Based on the source	Mode of administration	Mode of administration	Based on Sneha Paka	Based on combination	Based on benefits	Based on dose	Miscellaneous ^[3]
<i>Sthavara</i>	<i>Bahya</i>	<i>Accha sneha</i>	<i>Mridu</i>	<i>Yamaka</i>	<i>Sodana</i>	<i>Hrusiyasi</i>	<i>Sadya</i>
<i>Jangama</i>	<i>Abhyantara</i>	<i>Vicharana sneha</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Trivrut</i>	<i>Samana</i>	<i>Hrusva</i>	<i>Avapeedaka</i>
			<i>Khara</i>	<i>Mahan</i>	<i>Bruhmana</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Uttarabhaktika</i>
						<i>Uttama</i>	

In *urdhwajatru*, *taila* (oil) and *ghrita* (ghee) have various therapeutic uses.

Taila

- Considered beneficial for eyes (*chakshushya*), head and ears (*shira-karna*), and pain relief (*shoola prashamana*).^[5]
- Used in treatments such as *basti* (enema), *pana* (oral intake), *nasya* (nasal administration), and *karna-akshi purana* (ear and eye treatments).^[5]

Examples

- *Eranda taila*: Indicated for *vartmaja roga*.
- *Sarshapa taila*: Useful for *Karna - Shiro graha*.^[7]
- *Tila taila*: Useful for *shirashoola* (headaches), *chakshushya* (good for eyes), and can be used for ear and eye treatments (*Karna & Akshi purana*).^[6]

Ghrita

- Also considered *chakshushya* and *Agni Deepana* (digestive fire stimulation)^[8]

Types beneficial for eyes

- *Gavya & mahisha ghrita*.^[7]
- *Nuthana ghrita*: Beneficial in *netra roga* (eye diseases).^[7]
- *Nari, aja, and avika ghrita*: Also considered *chakshushya*.^[9]
- *Ksheertha ghrita*: Beneficial for eye diseases (*Netra roga*).^[9]
- All types of *ghrita* are recommended for *timira* (especially *kaumbha ghrita*).^[7]

CONSIDERATION OF PRAVICHARANA SNEHA IN THE CONTEXT OF SALAKYA ROGAS

Administration of *Sneha* with various preparations is known as *vicharana/pravicharana Sneha*.^[10] It also includes some of the external procedures like *abhyanga*, *karnapoorana*, *gandusha*, *nasya* & *akshitarpana* which are different treatment modalities adopted in *urdhwajatrugata rogas*.^[10]

CONSIDERATION OF ACCHA SNEHA IN THE CONTEXT OF SALAKYA ROGAS

Accha Sneha means administration of large quantity of *Sneha* without mixing with any food article or not with any *prakshepaka Dravya*. Among methods adopted for *Sneha Pana*, this is best & selected as first choice.^[10]

Different Snehana Procedures

1. ABHYANGA

Most popular form of *bahya snehana* which should be practiced daily as *dinacharya*. Practiced as *poorvakarma* for many other *snehana* & *svedana* procedures or practiced as *pradhana karma* too. Best treatment for controlling *vata*.^[3]

NETRA ROGAS-In case of *vataja abhishyanda*-After *ama pachana*, **ABHYANGA** is indicated.^[11]

KARNA ROGAS- In case of *vataja Karna shoola - vatahara Sneha Dravya* for *Abhyanga*. *Seeta veerya dravyas* for *pittaja Karna shoola*.^[12]

SHIRO ROGAS- In case of *vataja Shira shoola*, *Shiro abhyanga* is indicated,^[13] in case of *palithya- mayuradya ghrita* for *abhyanga*.^[14]

NASA ROGAS- In case of *vataja pratishyaya- Shiro abhyanga*, if pain is present, *Shiro abhyanga* is advised with *sukhoshna vatahara dravyas*.^[15]

MUKHA ROGAS- In *vataja osta prakopa -abhyanga* with *Chatur snehas + madhuchista*^[16] and also with *yastimadhu+lodra+sariva+shrvani+neelotpala+patola+kakamachi+tailam*. In *pittaja osta prakopa-abhyanga* with *ghrita* prepared from *guduchi+ Yasti Madhu+ Chandana+ ghrita*. In *vataja jihwa kantaka- Abhyanga* with *Chatur Sneha, Sneha pratisarana*. In case of *Galarbuda- abhyanga* with *Tikshna taila* is indicated.^[17]

Table 2: Abhyanga in Urdhwajatrugata vikaras.

Name of Procedure	Gata Roga	Name of Disease
<i>Abhyanga</i>	<i>Netra- Eye</i>	<i>Vataja Abhishyanda</i> ^[11]
	<i>Karna- Ear</i>	<i>Vataja Karna shoola</i> ^[12] <i>Pittaja Karna shoola</i> ^[12]
	<i>Shiras</i>	<i>Vataja Shira shoola</i> ^[13] <i>Pittaja Shira shoola</i> ^[13] <i>Upasheershaka</i> ^[14] <i>Palithya</i> ^[14]
	<i>Nasa</i>	<i>Vataja pratishyaya</i> ^[15]
	<i>Mukha</i>	<i>Vataja osta prakopa</i> ^[16] <i>Pittaja osta prakopa</i> <i>Vataja jihwa kantaka</i> <i>Vataja Rohini</i> ^[17] <i>Galarbuda</i> ^[17]

2. SNEHA PANA

It is a type of *abhyantara snehana* which involves the administration of medicated ghee in a specified quantity based on the disease condition.^[3]

NETRA ROGAS-In case of *kukunaka -Sneha panam* (with medicated *ghrita*) is given to *Dhatri*.^[18]

In case of *suktika*, the treatment principle is oral administration of *triphala ghrita* or *tilwaka ghrita* or *purana ghrita* for *virechana*.^[19] *Shashakadi ghrita panam* is given in case of *ajakajatha*.^[20] In case of *vataja abhishyanda* treatment principle adopted is *Sneha panam (ghrita pana)* after *ama pachana*.^[11] In *amladyushitha* - oral administration of *triphala ghrita*, *tilwaka ghrita*, *purana ghrita* is mentioned for *virechana*.^[17] Some of the *ghrita* preparations like *jeevantyadi ghrita*^[18],

patoladi ghrita^[21] & *triphala ghrita*^[18] are administered orally in case of *timira roga*.

KARNA ROGAS- In *vataja Karna shoola- vatahara Sneha dravyas* for *Sneha Pana*^[12]

SHIRO ROGAS- In *pittaja shira shoola- mridu virechana* is given by the oral administration of ghee prepared with *draksha*, *triphala*, *ikshurasa* & *ksheera*.^[19] In *Suryavartha*-Oral administration of ghee +*ksheera*.^[19]

MUKHA ROGAS- In *talv shosha- Uttarahaktika Sneha Pana, Pippali shunti-pakwa ghrita panam*^[20] In *Vataja Rohini- Sneha Pana*.^[20] In *Kaphaja galaganda*-Oral administration of *taila* prepared with the *Dravya* of *vatsakadi gana*.^[20]

Table 3: Sneha Pana in Urdhwajatrugata vikaras.

Name of Procedure	Gata Roga	Name of Disease
<i>Sneha pana</i>	<i>Netra- Eye</i>	<i>Kukunaka</i> ^[16] <i>Suktika Ajakajatha</i> <i>vataja abhishyanda</i> ^[11] <i>pittaja abhishyanda</i> ^[19] <i>kaphaja abhishyanda</i> ^[24] <i>raktaja abhishyanda</i> ^[28] <i>Adhi Mantha</i> ^[19,24,25] & <i>Sushka Akshi Paka</i> ^[26] <i>Amladyushitha Timira</i>
	<i>Karna- Ear</i>	<i>Vataja Karna shoola</i> ^[12]
	<i>Shiras</i>	<i>Vataja Shira shoola</i> ^[13] <i>Pittaja Shira shoola</i> ^[19] <i>Kaphaja Shira shoola</i> ^[13] <i>Suryavartha</i> ^[19]
	<i>Nasa</i>	<i>Vataja Pratishyaya</i> ^[24] <i>Pittaja Pratishyaya</i> ^[27] <i>Kaphaja Pratishyaya</i> ^[27] <i>Sannipataja Pratishyaya</i> ^[27] <i>Nasa anaha</i> ^[3]
	<i>Mukha</i>	<i>Talu shosha</i> ^[15] <i>Vataja Rohini</i> ^[15] <i>Kaphaja galaganda</i> ^[15]

3. NASYA KARMA- *Nasya karma* is a therapeutic measure where the medicated oil is administered through

nose to eliminate the vitiated dosha situated in *Shira* for the treatment of *urdhwajatrugata vikaras*.^[3]

Benefits

By performing *Nasya* (nasal administration of medicinal substances), diseases of the head and neck region subside. It brings clarity to the sense organs and imparts a pleasant fragrance to the mouth. It strengthens the jaws, teeth, head, neck, shoulders, arms, and chest. It also prevents the occurrence of wrinkles, premature greying of hair, baldness, and deformities.^[29]

NETRA ROGAS- In the context of *vartma rogas*, *snigda nasya* is told as *chikitsa* in *kruchronmeelana* which is a *vataja roga*.^[18] *Nasya karma* with the *ghrita* prepared from *madhura*, *seeta aushadha* in case of *pakshma shaatha*.^[18]

In *ajakajatha- nasya* with *Sasakadi gritha*.^[20] In case of *sushkaakshipaka – Jeevaneeya taila* or *anutaila nasyam* is mentioned.^[11] In *kaphaja timira- nasya* with *gomaya taila* is considered to be effective.^[30]

SHIRO ROGAS- In case of *palithya- nasya* with different *tailas & ghrita yogas* like *mayuradya ghrita* is indicated.^[14]

MUKHA ROGAS-In *danta veshtaka-Nasya* with *ghrita* prepared with *kakolyadi Dravya, dashaguna ksheera*.^[16] In *upakusha- nasya* with *ghrita* of *kakolyadi Dravya*.^[16] In *saushira-nasya* with *medicated ghrita* prepared with *sariva, Neela kamala, Yasti Madhu, lodra, agaru, Chandana*^[23] or 10 times *ksheera, ghrita*.^[16] In *talushosha-Ksheera Sarpi nasya*.^[23] In *Kaphaja Rohini-Nasya* with the *taila* prepared from *apamarga, aparajitha, vidanga, danti, saindhava lavana & taila*.^[25] In *Galarbuda- Nasya* with *Teekshna taila* is mentioned.^[25] In *Vataja Mukha Paka- Nasya* with *vatahara taila* or *ghrita*.^[25] In *Pittaja Mukha Paka- Nasya* with *seeta veerya, pittahara taila* or *ghrita* is indicated.^[25]

Table 4: Nasya karma in Urdhwajatrugata vikaras.

Name of Procedure	Gata Roga	Name of Disease
NASYA KARMA	Netra- Eye	<i>Kruchronmeelana</i> ^[18] <i>Pakshma shaata</i> ^[18] <i>Ajakajatha</i> ^[20] <i>Vataja abhishyanda</i> ^[11] <i>Pittaja</i> , ^[19] & <i>raktaja abhishyanda</i> ^[25] <i>Adhi Mantha</i> ^[11,19 &25] <i>Sushkaakshipaka</i> ^[11] <i>Kaphaja timira</i> ^[30]
	Karna- Ear	<i>Pittaja Karna shoola</i> ^[12]
	Shiras	<i>Vataja Shira shoola</i> ^[13] <i>Pittaja & Raktaja Shira shoola</i> ^[13] <i>Suryavarta & Ananthavatha</i> ^[13] <i>Palithya</i> ^[14]
	Nasa	<i>Vataja Pratishtaya</i> ^[27] <i>Pittaja Pratishtaya</i> ^[27] <i>Kaphaja Pratishtaya</i> ^[27] <i>Sannipataja Pratishtaya</i> ^[27] <i>Kshavathu</i> ^[28]
	Mukha	<i>Vataja osta prakopa</i> ^[16] <i>Sheetada</i> ^[16] <i>Danta veshtaka</i> ^[16] <i>Upakusha</i> ^[16] <i>Saushira</i> ^[23,16] <i>Danta Harsha</i> ^[16] <i>Vataja jihwa kantaka</i> ^[16] <i>Talushosha</i> ^[23] <i>Kaphaja Rohini</i> ^[25] <i>Gala arbudha</i> ^[25] <i>Vataja Mukha Paka</i> ^[25] <i>Pittaja Mukha Paka</i> ^[25]

4. AKSHI TARPANA-It is one among the *bahya snehana* practiced over eyes. One among the *netra kriya kalpa* which is done for nourishing eyes. Procedure where in a circular ring prepared of black gram powder is fixed around the eyes & filled with milk etc. liquids & person is made to blink his eyes for certain *matra kala* based on disease condition.^[31]

NETRA ROGAS-In diseases like- *vataja abhishyanda, Adhi Mantha*^[11], *sushkaakshipaka (jeevaneeya ghrita tarpana)*.^[29]

5. SHIROBASTI

The procedure wherein the lukewarm oil is made to keep over the head using leather cap.^[3]

SHIRO ROGAS-In case of *Vataja shira shoola*^[13], *Suryavartha (Shiro Basti with Chatur Sneha Sarpi)*^[13], *Anantha vata*.^[13]

MUKHA ROGAS-*Hanu moksha*^[16], *vataja osta prakopa (Shiro basti with vatahara taila ex: -Balataila or ksheerabala taila)*.^[16]

NASA ROGAS- *Kshavathu*^[28]

NETRA ROGAS-*Vataja abhishyanda & Adhi Mantha*^[11]

6. KARNA PURANA

Procedure of instilling lukewarm medicated liquids into the ears & retained for a stipulated time.^[3]

By regularly performing *Karna Purana* (the practice of oiling the ears), one does not suffer from ear diseases caused by *Vata*, nor does one experience stiffness in the neck and jaw. Hearing difficulties or deafness do not occur, and the hearing remains clear. *Karna Purana* (ear oiling) alleviates pain in the jaw, neck, head, and ears.^[29]

KARNA ROGAS- *Vataja Karna shola*,^[32] *kaphaja Karna shola*,^[32] *Karna nada*^[32] & *Karna kshweda*,^[32] *Poothi Karna*,^[32] *Krimi Karna*,^[12] *Karna gootha*^[12]

7. Gandusha & Kavala

The procedure wherein the medicated liquid is filled mouth full & retained for a stipulated period is called as *gandusha*.^[3]

Benefits

By holding oil in the mouth (*Gandusha*), the strength of the jaws and voice improves, and the face becomes well-developed. It enhances the sense of taste and provides excellent appetite. There will be no dryness in the throat, no fear of lips cracking, and the teeth will not decay; they become strong at the roots. They do not loosen or become sensitive and are able to chew even the hardest food items.^[29]

KAVALA

The procedure wherein the mouth is filled with medicated liquids and moved inside the oral cavity is called *Kavala*.^[33]

Benefits

By practicing *Kavala* (gargling), diseases of the neck, head, ears, mouth, and eyes are alleviated. It also helps with excessive salivation, throat ailments, dryness of the mouth, nausea, lethargy, loss of taste, and nasal congestion.^[34]

MUKHA ROGAS-In *sheetada- Kavala graha* with *ksheera*.^[23] In *upakusha-Kavala* with *ghrita* prepared from *kakolyadi Madhura Dravya*.^[16] *Vataja Rohini-Sukhoshna gandusha* with *Chatur Sneha*,^[16] *Pittaja Rohini- gandusha*,^[16] *Kaphaja Rohini- gandusha* with

the *taila* prepared from *apamarga, aparajitha, vidanga, danti, saindhava lavana & taila*.^[23]

DISCUSSION

The word *snehana* includes both *bahya* and *abhyantara snehana*. The *karmukata* or the mode of action of different *snehana* procedures are given below.

Abhyanga- Dalhana has explained in detail the absorption of *Sneha* used in *Abhyanga* procedure, accordingly the oil used in *Abhyanga* reaches up to the different *Dhatu* if it is applied for the sufficient time. Hence, it is clear that the drug used in the *Abhyanga* gets absorbed by the skin. Dalhana also mentions that when *Snehana* drug reaches to the particular *Dhatu* and it subsides the diseases of that particular *Dhatu*. Charaka has also described that *Vayu* dominates in the *Sparshanendriya* and its *Adhishthana* is *Tvacha* i.e. skin. The *Abhyanga* is exceedingly beneficial to the skin. Acharya Sushruta in *Shareera Sthana* explains - Out of the four *Tiryak Dhamanis*, each divides gradually hundred and thousand times and thus become innumerable. These cover the body like network and their openings are attached to *Romakooa*. Through these, only *Veerya* of *Abhyanga dravya* enter into the body after undergoing *Paka* with *Bhrajaka Pitta* in skin and shows its action.^[35]

The mode of action of *Abhyanga* can also be understood by the properties of *Snehana* drugs that are used for *Abhyanga* as the properties of the *Snehana* drugs are opposite to *Vata*, it is useful in the diseases caused by vitiated *Vata*. Through touch, massage works on the nervous system. According to modern human physiology the skin functions as a major sense organ. There are millions of nerve endings underneath the skin which serve as receivers for the body, keeping it informed of changes in the surroundings. Specialised receptors make it possible for the body to detect sensations of light touch (*Meissner's corpuscles*) and pressure (*Pacinian corpuscles*) as well as pain, heat and cold.^[36]

SNEHA PANA- *Sneha* loosens the *Doshas* which are adherent to the walls of minute channels. Charkha has given simile that as from oil smeared container, the water can be easily separated without much effort, and similarly *Kaphadi Doshas* are easily expelled out from the oiled body. The main purpose of *Purvakarma* is to bring *Doshas* from *Shakha* to *Koshta*. It is done by *Snehana* and *Swedana*. Acharya Charaka has described about movement of *Doshas* from *Shakha* to the *Koshta*. Acharya Sushruta explains that due to *Snehana* and *Swedana*, the morbid *doshas* become liquefied and brought to *Koshta* for easy elimination by the *shodhana*. Different measures employed for bringing *doshas* to *Koshta* are *Vridhi*, *Vishyandana*, *Paka* and *Srotomukha-Vishodhana*. *Snehana karma* achieves these with the help of its *Gunas*. *Sneha* is having *Ap* as its predominant *Mahabhuta* and spreads in the body due to its *Drava* and *Sukshma Swabhava* and helps in liquefying the *doshas*

due to its Snigdha, Mridu, Drava and Sara properties. It penetrates Srotas and removes Sroto Sanga, which is one of the important steps in the samprapti Vighatana, allowing proper movement of dosha.^[37]

NASYA KARMA- *Nasa* is the gateway to *shira*. Nose to brain route is used to deliver drug to the systemic circulation through absorption into the blood vessels underlying the nasal mucosa. The nasal cavity has a rich vascular supply and a direct connection to the brain through the olfactory and trigeminal nerves. Administering medications nasally allows for quick and efficient delivery of drugs to the central nervous system, bypassing the blood-brain barrier. This can help in relieving congestion, sinusitis, and other respiratory conditions. By stimulating the hypothalamus and pituitary glands, *Nasya Karma* can help in regulating hormonal imbalances and improving endocrine function.^[3]

AKSHI TARPANA- The *ghrita* has the quality of trespassing into minute channels of the body. The lipophilic action of *ghrita* facilitate the transportation of the drug to the target organ and finally reaching the cell, because the cell membrane also contains lipid. This lipophilic nature of *ghrita* facilitates the entry of drug into the eyeball through the corneal surface. *Ghrita* provides essential lipids and moisture, helping maintain stromal integrity and hydration, indirectly preventing stromal thinning or degeneration. Herbal components of *Ghrita* provide antioxidants, reducing oxidative stress in keratocytes. Regular Tarpana may help in collagen remodelling, contributing to corneal stability.^[38]

SHIRO BASTI- *Sneha*, a lipid material, nourishes different nervous system components by quickly passing through the blood-brain barrier. Further, absorbed active principles of *taila* reach up to nerves and exert their *vatagna* effects. *Snigdhatata* of this *taila* removes the *rukshata* of vitiated *vata*, which helps nourish nerve functions. *Mridu abhyanga* after the procedure also helps improve the impulse transmission in the nerve and synapses by influencing the activity of neurotransmitters.^[39]

KARNA PURANA- Before *Karnapoorana*, *Abhyanga* is specifically done in *Murdha Pradesha* which causes vasodilatation in the skin and muscles by stimulating receptors of the sympathetic nervous system. Vasodilatation increases blood flow, and it makes the channels soft, by which *Vatadi Doshas* and other contents can flow through in their normal directions. For example, in *Badhirya* restores mechanical and nervous transmission, enhances sound wave conduction, and strengthens auditory nerve endings.^[40]

GANDUSHA & KAVALA- The process exerts mechanical pressure inside the oral cavity which in turn stimulates the stretch reflex (pressoreceptors). These receptors send signal to salivary nuclei in brainstem

(Pons and Medulla). This causes an increase in parasympathetic activity and the motor fibres of 7th and 9th cranial nerve (Facial and Glossopharyngeal) trigger the production of saliva. An enzyme lysosome present in saliva causes an increase in the local defense mechanism. Gargling inhibits plaque accumulation and adhesion of food substances which may further be a cause for dental caries. *Vranaropaka* drugs like *Ghrita* provide local calming effect and ease the pain and ulceration. The drug increases vascular permeability due to irritation of oral mucosa and *Sukhoshna* (lukewarm) temperature.^[41]

CONCLUSION

Snehana is a highly effective treatment for *Urdhwajatrugata rogas*. By incorporating *Snehana* into one's treatment plan, individuals can experience significant improvements in their symptoms, quality of life, and overall well-being. It is not necessary that *snehana* should be practiced only in case of diseases, rather it can be advised in a healthy person too for maintenance of health. For example-*abhyanga*, *Karna purana*, *gandusha* etc. which is why all these procedures are explained under *dinacharya* & *ritucharya*. If we practice *dinacharya* & *ritucharya* in our day-to-day basis it is not needed to take it as a treatment, nor we suffer from any diseases. Human body is the *sara* or essence of *Sneha*. Each part of the body either formed or nourished by the *Sneha*. *Dosha*, *dhatu*, *mala*, *indriya* all need *Sneha* for its formation, maintenance or for optimum functioning.

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